

THE REACTIVITY OF SULFHYDRYL GROUPS IN PROTEINS. PART II. LYSOZYME AND OVALBUMIN

BY R. LONTIE AND G. BECKERS

Various types of specific thiol reagents were allowed to react on lysozyme and ovalbumin, both native and denatured. An attempt has been made to interpret the differences of reactivity observed in the light of the Pauling-Corey structural theories. The hypothesis of intramolecular hydrogen bonds, involving cysteinic thiol and peptidic carbonyl groups, is brought forward to explain certain differences of reactivity of native ovalbumin.

Since the work of Hellerman *et al.* on urease (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1943, 157, 443), the distinction between "freely reacting", sluggish" and "masked" SH groups among the sulfhydryl groups of a protein has become classical. The first reacts with all the thiol reagents, the second with the stronger reagents only, while the masked groups become accessible to reagents only after denaturation.

Much experimental data are already available on this subject, showing similar differences of reactivity in other proteins. Several interpretations have also been proposed, but none are fully satisfactory. Still, before attempting to explain these differences, it seems that a doubt concerning the validity of comparison of the data is to be cleared. SH reactions are deeply influenced by the conditions of the reaction. Most of the authors, however, worked with a single reagent on one or a few proteins. Too often they prepared or denatured their proteins according to different methods. The determinations were performed under different conditions of concentration, temperature, p_H , ionic strength, time etc., and in quite a few papers, all these conditions were not even specified. Hence, the ambiguity of a comparison of such data may be ascribed to the discrepancies arising out of the differences in the conditions of operation. To dismiss such a doubt, a few critically chosen methods were applied under standard conditions to one and the same solution of each of a few proteins, both in their native state and after denaturation in a 7.5M-urea solution. Silver, *p*-chloromercuribenzoate and ferricyanide determinations were conducted according to the methods described in Part I (this issue, p. 285).

Iodoacetic Acid and Iodoacetamide.—Alkylating reagents are the mildest among the three types of commonly used SH reagents. Iodoacetamide and iodoacetic acid were selected. Rosner's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 132, 657) was followed with a few modifications and the replacement of the colorimeter by a spectrophotometer. Under our conditions of work, the alkylating reagents react also with methionine, but more slowly (Hermans, Thesis, Leuven, 1951). The very slow reaction with the amino groups is important owing to their number (Michaelis and Schubert, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, 106, 331). A rise of temperature or p_H increases considerably the velocity of the reactions. These remarks, and more could be made, show the importance of a perfect standardisation of the methods to ensure a significant comparison of data.

The iodoacetamide was synthesised by Anson's method (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1939, 22, 247) and the monoiodoacetic acid, according to Abderhalden (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2852). The starch solution was prepared according to Gross (*Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 900). The iodine solution in presence of starch shows, under our conditions of operation, a maximum absorption at $5800\text{\AA}$, increased by 25% through dilution with an equal volume of a saturated $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution. But for minute concentrations, the relation between extinction and iodine concentration is perfectly linear.

The determinations were conducted as follows: 15 ml. of a 3% protein solution and 15 ml. of distilled water were introduced in separate glass-stoppered flasks; 15 ml. of the 1% alkylating reagent solution, buffered at neutrality, was added to both. All solutions were prestabilised at 25° . The flasks were placed in a thermostat and, at determined times, 4 ml. of the reacting mixture was pipetted into centrifugation tubes, where the reaction was abruptly stopped by addition of 3 ml. of a 3.3% sulphosalicylic acid solution. The precipitated protein was centrifuged and the supernatant liquid filtered into a 20 ml. volumetric flask. The washing sulphosalicylic solution was added up to the mark. If the amount of I^- formed was expected to be small, 0.8 ml. of a 0.002M-KI solution was pre-added to the blank and protein solutions so as to reach the threshold of linearity in the extinction curves. The solutions (5 ml.) were pipetted into small Erlenmeyer flasks and 5 ml. of a saturated solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 2 ml. starch solution and 3 drops of perhydrol were added. When a large amount of I^- was expected to be liberated, a convenient dilution with the sulphosalicylic acid solution was made in the first stage. Extinctions were measured at $5800\text{\AA}$ and at 25° with a Beckman DU. The operations on the filtrate were repeated 2 to 3 times, and the average extinction recorded. The amount of I^- liberated was determined by reading the amount corresponding to the difference between extinctions of blank and protein solutions on pre-established standard curves. These were made from known KI solutions. The quantities of I^- liberated in terms of time of reaction were recorded on a graph. By extrapolating to zero time the "free SH groups" were determined. The slope of the curves provides indications about the other reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lysozyme

Crystallised lysozyme was prepared according to Alderton *et al.* (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1945, 157, 43; 1946, 164, 1).

Four argentometric titrations were performed with each of the native, urea- and heat-denatured protein solutions. No SH group was detected. This corresponds with the results of the amino-acid analysis which accounts for no cysteine. The presence of a large amount of cystine (8%) confirms the fact that under our conditions of operation, the silver leaves disulphide bonds untouched in proteins. In view of these findings, it is difficult to see how the hypothesis of Burk (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 20, 63) that the appearance of the "masked SH groups" after denaturation is due to the breaking of disulphide bonds by the denaturing agents, could still be defended.

Ovalbumin

Crystallised ovalbumin was prepared according to Sørensen *et al.* (*Compt. rend. Trav. Lab. Carlsberg*, 1917, 12, 68). The solutions A, B, C and D were prepared directly from egg white and E, from egg white first treated with bentonite to obtain the lysozyme. The M. W. of 45,000 (Bull. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, 137, 143) and N-content of 15.8% (Lewis *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, 186, 23) were adopted.

TABLE I

Soln.	Ag(NH ₃) ₂ ⁺		p-ClHg-b.		Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻		ICH ₂ COO ²⁻ SH/M.	ICH ₂ CONH ₂ SH/M.
	SH/M.	No detts.	SH/M.	No.	SH/M.	No.		
Native egg albumin								
A	5.6	2						0.1
B	4.8	3	3.2	9	0	3		
C	5.6	3						
D	5.5	6						
E	4.4	2	3.2	5	1.2	3		
Lit.	...		2.3-3.5	Mc.Do.	0	My. & An.		0 Lar.
Egg albumin denatured with 7.5M urea.								
C	4.1	3	5.5	5	1/2hr 2	2		
					1hr. 2.7	2		
					30hr. 1.8	2		
B							3.25	
Lit.					3.6 My.		3.1-3.4 Ro.	3

No. for number of separate determinations; average result recorded. Mac Donnell (*loc. cit.*); Mirsky & Anson (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1936, 19, 451); Rosner (*loc. cit.*); Larson & Jenness (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3090); Mirsky (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1941, 24, 709).

Alkylating reagents do not afford an immediate reaction with the SH groups of

native egg albumin. If the protein, however, is kept sufficiently long in contact with iodoacetamide, and denatured after the iodoacetamide has been washed away, the SH reagents react with 2 SH/mol. less than they normally do. A slow reaction with iodoacetamide before denaturation was accordingly surmised (Anson, *loc. cit.*, 1940; Larson, *loc. cit.*). The slope of the curves (Fig. 1) directly confirms this hypothesis: for the first 10 hours the slope of the iodoacetamide reaction with the native protein is steep while that of iodoacetate is practically non-existent. We know that SH reactions are swifter with iodoacetamide than with iodoacetate (Dickens, *Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1141), while with most amines it is the velocity of

FIG. 1

I⁻ equiv. liberated per mol. of protein in terms of time.

Curves marked with black dots and circles represent respectively the reaction of iodoacetate and iodoacetamide with native and urea-denatured ovalbumin.

the iodoacetate reaction which is greater (Michaelis and Schubert, *loc. cit.*). It may then be safely concluded that the two iodine equivalents liberated within the first 10 hours of the reaction are due to slow iodoacetamide-SH reaction.

DISCUSSION

Ovalbumin has been the most extensively studied protein concerning SH reactions. Our conclusions are based on the literature as well as on our own results. References to papers reviewed by Anson (*Adv. Prot. Chem.*, 1945, 2, 361), Neurath *et al.* (*Chem. Rev.*, 1944, 34, 157), Herriott (*Adv. Prot. Chem.*, 1947, 3, 170) and Barron (*Adv. Enzym.*, 1951, 11, 201) have been omitted. Four groups of phenomena call for interpretation:

1. *The reactivity of "masked SH groups" after denaturation.*—From the amino-acid analysis, 5-6 cysteine radicals per mol. could be expected. Silver reacts with 5.5SH/mol. in the native protein, *i.e.*, probably all the SH groups present. Ovalbumin is in fact a mixture of two closely similar proteins in proportions varying according to the sample. They possess different electrophoretic mobilities at certain p_n , but have not been fractionated (Longworth *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2580). One component possesses probably 5 cysteine/mol. and the other 6. Other reagents than silver attack either some of the groups or none. After denaturation in a 7.5 *M*-urea solution, however, all "masked" groups react with β -ClHg-b, 2-3 groups with ferricyanide and other oxidising agents, 3 with the alkylating agents. Many similar observations are reported for other reagents and denaturing agents. A comprehensive explanation of these phenomena is required, as groups other than the thiols are also masked in native proteins.

The picture of denaturation in the light of the Pauling-Corey structural theories seems to account satisfactorily for the increase of reactive groups.

Native ovalbumin shows the α -keratin X-ray diagram, related by Pauling to twisted α -helixes. The molecule is formed of a single polypeptide of about 400 amino-acids. It appears to be a cylinder or an ellipsoid, 90-100Å high with a diameter of 26-32Å. The helix is thus plaited, to form the "7 strand coiled coil" suggested by Pauling or some similar structure. Physicochemical studies have led to represent the molecule of denatured ovalbumin in solution as a rigid rod of 600Å in length. It indicates that it is a simple helix with 1.5Å per radical. Moreover, the X-ray diagram remains characteristic of the α -helix. Finally, by the action of a drastic agent or of some mechanical force, the denatured molecule acquires the β -keratin structure, corresponding to a plaited sheet configuration.

Thus, the denaturation of ovalbumin consists in the rupture of weak intrapeptidic bonds, resulting in a progressive unfolding of the "coiled coil", accompanied eventually by local uncoiling of the helix itself. In partially denatured ovalbumin, there seems to be an equilibrium mixture between native and denatured protein. Practically all of the latter exist under a single form corresponding to the actual chemical environment (Strachitskii and Plotnikova, *Ukrain Biokhim. Zhur.*, 1948, 20, 187). Denatured molecules tend to aggregate by the formation of disulphide intermolecular bonds (Halwer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 183). The reactivity of SH groups increases with this unfolding, as would be expected. Where closely intertwined, plaited helixes predominate, the side chains will be involved in bonds of different types, either with nearby radicals or with the very imino and carbonyl groups of the chains, or they will be coiled

up in the "holes" of the helices. The rigid structure stabilises the otherwise weak bonds; it maintains also a fixed constellation of radicals surrounding the non-peripheral reactive groups, and thus renders them inaccessible to certain reagents. With the unfolding and eventual local uncoiling of the helices, however, many electrostatic and steric hindrances are removed, stabilised intrapeptidic bonds are broken, and the side radicals regain a large degree of freedom that enables them to react more easily.

Some parallel observations are enlightening. Bull (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 133, 39) showed that the viscosity of an ovalbumin solution increased notably with denaturation by heat, more so in presence of urea. Connecting viscosity with the assymetry of the molecule, he calculated that the axial ratio passed from 3.9 to 7.4 and 9.2 respectively. These ratios manifest a progressive unfolding to which may be connected an increased SH reactivity (e.g., Mirsky, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1941, 24, 709; by ferricyanide: 0; 2; 3.6 SH/mol. respectively).

2. *Spontaneous oxidation by air of some thiols of denatured ovalbumin.*—Fewer SH groups (4.1/5.6) were detected by silver after urea-denaturation. Benesch (*Arch. Biochem.*, 1948, 19, 35) made similar observations on ovalbumin denatured with guanidine, alcohol and duponol. The spontaneous oxidation of thiols to disulphides by air is known. The reaction velocity increases with the temperature, p_H and the presence of traces of metals (Barron, *Biochem. J.*, 1927, 41, 62). We may thus expect oxidation to occur in denatured ovalbumin whenever two SH groups come sufficiently close together. Intermolecular bonds are surely created that way and aggregates formed (Halwer, *loc. cit.*). We attribute the decrease of the silver reaction to such oxidations, occurring in the time between the preparation of the buffered ammoniacal solution and the end of the titration ($\frac{1}{2}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ hour). The greater freedom enjoyed by the unfolded molecules, as denaturation proceeds, allows SH groups to come in such closeness as to permit the formation of disulphide bonds. These reactions will follow the general rules of thiol oxidation. We may thus expect a much swifter oxidation by air at the p_H 9.25 of the silver titration than at the neutral p_H of the other methods (so p -ClHg-b reacts with all the SH groups [5.5] after denaturation).

The percentage of spontaneously oxidised thiols is bound to increase also with longer times of contact of the protein with the denaturing agent. This would explain the ferricyanide titrations. There is at first a slight increase of SH groups titrated (2 to 2.7 SH/mol.) with longer time of contact with urea ($\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hr.). The unfolding is probably still progressing. This increase is reversed (2.7 to 1.8 SH/mol.) by spontaneous oxidation, if the time of contact is unduly prolonged (1 to 30 hr.). Rosner (*loc. cit.*) observed a similar decrease in his titrations of denatured ovalbumin using iodoacetate. So did Hopkins with nitroprusside (*Nature*, 1933, 126, 328). These phenomena show the importance of a perfect standardisation of the methods. It would be safer to conduct the denaturation at a low p_H (5.5) and neutralise the solutions just before the titrations.

3. *The different reactivity of the thiols of native ovalbumin with different specific reagents.*—The responsibility for the differential reactivity of the SH groups of native ovalbumin, under identical conditions, with the different specific reagents may be attributed to three main causes:

(a). Mild oxidising agents affect no thiols in native ovalbumin (ferricyanide, porphyrindine, arsenoxide, 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol, etc.). Thiols, in close proximity with each other only, can be oxidised into disulphides. There are presumably no such thiols in native ovalbumin.

Data of titrations by oxidising agents must be carefully handled. The specificity of their SH reaction is always doubtful.

(b). Thiols could be rendered inaccessible to certain reagents due to steric or electrostatic hindrances brought about by neighbouring chains. The inhibitory effect of valine in the polarographic reduction of phenacetyl-L-cysteinyl-D-valine mercaptides, and its disappearance in urea solution are suggestive in that line (Benesch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4367). For lack of knowledge regarding the amino-acid sequence, however, such interpretations of a differential reactivity in proteins remain questionable.

We must notice the complete titration of ovalbumin SH groups by the small silver ion (5.5 SH/mol.) and their incomplete titration by equally strong but cumbersome *p*-ClHg-b (3.1 SH/mol.), while the cysteyl-valine sequence has been found to be one of the important dipeptides in ovalbumin hydrolysates (Flavin, *Nature*, 1954, **173**, 214).

(c). Proteinic thiols seem capable of forming hydrogen bonds. Further work on the subject is being carried on and details will be published later. Some points may be mentioned here. The possibility of hydrogen bonds involving an SH group as proton donor is now-a-days established. The strength of the bond is proportional to the ionic character of the thiol. Accordingly, alkylmercaptans form only weak bonds (specially Gordy and Stanford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 497). Yet, from the general conditions of hydrogen-bond formation, it appears that favourable atomic distances and bond angles could stabilise an otherwise weak bond. This is the case in many instances of chelation, involving Cl, Br or certain C atoms. In a molecular model of an α -helix, besides other possibilities, favourable conditions seem to exist for the formation of hydrogen bond between the sulphur of a cysteinyl side chain and the oxygen of its carboxy group. Bond distances and angles are such as to allow the formation of a six-membered ring (including the H atom). The co-planarity of the carbonyl group and α -carbon is imposed by resonance in the peptide linkage. The electronegativity of the oxygen is greatly enhanced for the same reason. Inferring from analogous structures and X-ray data, we expect the structure with a co-planer β -carbon to be favoured. Only the SH group would enjoy a large freedom of rotation. Keeping normal bond angles and distances, a vector from the S atom to the O atom could be deflected only by a few degrees from the SH direction, while the distance between the H and O atoms would be of about 1.5 Å, if the C_{β} -S bond forms an angle of about 50° with the CO-C $_{\alpha}$ -C $_{\beta}$ plane. The increase in ionic character noted for the thiol of glutathione as compared with that of cysteine (Cecil, *Biochem. J.*, 1950, **47**, 572) could find here its explanation. On the other hand, we have noticed that the reactions of cysteine with silver and *p*-ClHg-b in electron-donor solutions are quantitative. The latter, however, affect the reactions with ferricyanide and easily reduce by one half the reactions of the alkylating reagents. The effects observed were found to be a function of the basicity and concentration of electron-donor (Beckers, Thesis, Louvain, 1953). Benesch (*loc. cit.*, 1953) supplies an interesting counter-proof. In the

presence of urea, the nitroprusside reaction of cysteine is increased by 50%, that of three cysteinic tripeptides, by 100%, whereas the reactions with Na_2S and ethylmercaptan are unaffected by the presence of urea.

To sum up: hydrogen bonds involving the thiols are likely to occur in proteins, and such bonds seem to affect the reactions of thiols with mild reagents and not those with stronger ones. Hence, new possibilities of discrimination in the action of specific reagents.

We are inclined to think that the three thiols of native ovaalbumin which afford no reaction with iodoacetate and other reagents, a very slow and partial reaction with iodoacetamide and which react normally both with silver and $p\text{-ClHg-b}$, fall under this heading. These may even be the groups that remain "sluggish" after denaturation, while the other two groups become accessible by unfolding of the molecule.

(d). *Discrepancies in the titrations of an apparently identical protein with the same reagent.*—We notice appreciable differences between the titrations of the E solution of ovalbumin and the other solutions. The silver reagent titrates only 4.4SH/mol. instead of 5.5 SH, and by ferricyanide we detect 1.2 SH/mol. instead of 0.

This is the place to stress the importance of a perfect standardisation in the mode of preparation of the protein. When a protein is a mixture of two components, we can always expect that the proportions may vary according to the mode of preparation. Conditions under which oxidation of SH groups by air could be enhanced, such as high p_a , contact with worn brass agitator etc., should be avoided. The same must be said of procedures that could provoke a partial denaturation.

The E solution was prepared from egg white first treated with bentonite to extract the lysozyme. The suspension was homogenised in a Waring blender. Likely, the mechanical agitation provoked a beginning of denaturation (cf. Wu and Ling, *Chinese J. Physiol.*, 1927, 1, 407) that manifested itself by the availability of one "masked" SH group. It would be the one titrated directly by ferricyanide and oxidised by air in the solution buffered at p_H 9.25 for the silver titration.

LABORATORY OF BIOCHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF LOUVAIN, BELGIUM,
AND
ST XAVIER'S COLLEGE, CALCUTTA-6.

Received April 1, 1955.